

ON THE 82-TH SMARANDACHE'S PROBLEM

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the asymptotic properties of the integer part of the k -th root positive integer, and give two interesting asymptotic formulae.

Keywords: k -th root; Integer part; Asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction And Results

For any positive integer n , let $s_k(n)$ denote the integer part of k -th root of n . For example, $s_k(1) = 1$, $s_k(2) = 1$, $s_k(3) = 1$, $s_k(4) = 1, \dots$, $s_k(2^k) = 2$, $s_k(2^k + 1) = 2, \dots$, $s_k(3^k) = 3, \dots$. In problem 82 of [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the sequence $s_k(n)$. About this problem, some authors had studied it, and obtained some interesting results. For instance, the authors [5] used the elementary method to study the mean value properties of $S(s_k(n))$, where Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as following:

$$S(n) = \min\{m : m \in N, n \mid m!\}.$$

In this paper, we use elementary method to study the asymptotic properties of this sequence in the following form: $\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)}$ and $\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{\varphi(s_k(n))}$, where $x \geq 1$ be a real number, $\varphi(n)$ be the Euler totient function, and give two interesting asymptotic formulae. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem 1. *For any real number $x > 1$ and any fixed positive integer $k > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} = \frac{6}{\pi^2}x + O\left(x^{1-\frac{1}{k}-\varepsilon}\right),$$

where ε is any real number.

Theorem 2. For any real number $x > 1$ and any fixed positive integer $k > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{\varphi(s_k(n))} = \frac{k\zeta(2)\zeta(3)}{(k-1)\zeta(6)} x^{1-\frac{1}{k}} + A + O\left(x^{1-\frac{2}{k}} \log x\right),$$

$$\text{where } A = \gamma \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^2(n)}{n\varphi(n)} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^2(n) \log n}{n\varphi(n)}.$$

§2. Proof of Theorems

In this section, we will complete the proof of Theorems. First we come to prove Theorem 1. For any real number $x > 1$, let M be a fixed positive integer with $M^k \leq x \leq (M+1)^k$, from the definition of $s_k(n)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} &= \sum_{t=1}^M \sum_{(t-1)^k \leq n < t^k} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} + \sum_{M^k \leq n < x} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^{M-1} \sum_{t^k \leq n < (t+1)^k} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} + \sum_{M^k \leq n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(M)}{M} \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^{M-1} [(t+1)^k - t^k] \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} + O\left(\sum_{M^k \leq n < (M+1)^k} \frac{\varphi(M)}{M}\right) \\ &= k \sum_{t=1}^M t^{k-1} \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} + O\left(M^{k-1-\varepsilon}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where we have used the estimate $\frac{\varphi(n)}{n} \ll n^{-\varepsilon}$.

Note that (see reference [3])

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(n)}{n} = \frac{6}{\pi^2} x + O\left((\log x)^{\frac{2}{3}} (\log \log x)^{\frac{4}{3}}\right). \quad (2)$$

Let $B(y) = \sum_{t \leq y} \frac{\varphi(t)}{t}$, then by Abel's identity (see Theorem 4.2 of [2]) and (2), we can easily deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t=1}^M t^{k-1} \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} &= M^{k-1} B(M) - B(1) - (k-1) \int_1^M y^{k-2} B(y) dy \\ &= M^{k-1} \left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} M + O\left((\log M)^{\frac{2}{3}} (\log \log M)^{\frac{4}{3}}\right) \right) \\ &\quad - (k-1) \int_1^M \left(y^{k-2} \left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} y + O\left((\log y)^{\frac{2}{3}} (\log \log y)^{\frac{4}{3}}\right) \right) \right) dy \\ &= \frac{6}{k\pi^2} M^k + O\left((\log M)^{\frac{2}{3}} (\log \log M)^{\frac{4}{3}}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Applying (1) and (3) we can obtain the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} = \frac{6}{\pi^2} M^k + O\left(M^{k-1-\varepsilon}\right). \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, note that the estimate

$$0 \leq x - M^k < (M+1)^k - M^k \ll x^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \quad (5)$$

Now combining (4) and (5) we can immediately obtain the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\varphi(s_k(n))}{s_k(n)} = \frac{6}{\pi^2} x + O\left(x^{1-\frac{1}{k}-\varepsilon}\right).$$

This proves Theorem 1.

Similarly, note that (see reference [4])

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} = \frac{\zeta(2)\zeta(3)}{\zeta(6)} \log x + A + O\left(\frac{\log x}{x}\right),$$

where $A = \gamma \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^2(n)}{n\varphi(n)} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^2(n) \log n}{n\varphi(n)}$. We can use the same method to obtain the result of Theorem 2.

References

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